

***In vitro* Regeneration of Sugarcane Varieties via Indirect Organogenesis**

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ABSTRACT

Sugarcane (*Saccharum spp.*) is an important economic crop that accounts for 70-80% of global sugar production. Nigerian domestic sugar production accounts for only 2.7% of the nation's sugar consumption. Establishment of commercial sugarcane plantation requires a large number of planting material, which is difficult to obtain using the conventional method of propagation due to low multiplication rate and transmission of diseases from one generation to another. Tissue culture is a formidable tool that can be used for micro-propagation and genetic improvement of sugarcane. This work was carried out to develop a protocol for micropropagation of sugarcane using indirect organogenesis. Callus was established on Murashige and Skoog media fortified with 2, 4-Dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2, 4-D) after incubation in the dark for four weeks. Shoot regeneration was achieved following culture of embryonic callus on regeneration media consisting of MS basal supplemented with 6-Benzylaminopurine (BAP) + Naphthalene acetic acid (NAA). Efficient regeneration of both embryogenic and non-embryogenic callus was achieved on media containing 2.5 mg/L 2, 4-D. Application of 2.5 mg/L or 3.0 mg/L BAP with 0.5 mg/L NAA significantly increased the regeneration capacity of the embryogenic callus. The Sugarcane varieties significantly varied in regeneration potential, with the highest regeneration recorded in M21-1988 and BD9800. The protocol could be adapted for the mass production of sugarcane planting materials and the subsequent establishment of a commercial plantation in Nigeria.

Keywords: Indirect organogenesis, Sugarcane, 2, 4-D, Callus, *in vitro*, Regeneration

INTRODUCTION

Sugarcane (*Saccharum spp.*) is an essential economic crop that belongs to the grass family Poaceae. It accounts for 70-80% of sugar production worldwide (Thorat *et al.* 2017). Sugarcane is believed to have originated from the Indonesia/New Guinea region, where it has been cultivated as a garden crop since 8000 B.C. (Dula, 2021). Modern sugarcane varieties are believed to be complex interspecific hybrids between *S. officinarum* with nearby grass species like *Miscanthus*, *Erianthus*, and *Nerenga* (Altpeter *et al.*, 2010).

In Nigeria, sugarcane is cultivated for both vegetable and industrial use, making it a significant cash crop in the country. The Nigerian sugar consumption is estimated at 1.56 million tons, and domestic production fluctuates between 0 – 2.7% in the last 30 years (www.nsdcnigeria.org). In 2020, for example, Nigeria expanded an estimated 7.64 billion dollars (10.7 trillion naira) for the import of sugar. In the last 30 years, Nigerian sugar import was valued at 14.7 billion dollars (20.58 trillion naira). The backward integration was introduced to reduce the import-dependent consumption of the commodity. However,

Nigerian domestic sugar production did not exceed 2.7% of the nation's sugar consumption. One key reason for low domestic sugar production in Nigeria is poorly developed sugar plantations in the country. Sugarcane is propagated vegetatively using stem cuttings due to low seed yield and poor seed quality. This method is associated with a low rate of multiplication, which makes large-scale production of sugarcane difficult.

Tissue culture is a powerful tool for micro-propagation and genetic improvement of sugarcane. This technology can facilitate the mass propagation of elite sugarcane genotypes and enable the establishment of sugarcane plantations within just 1 to 2 years. Previous studies have reported on the regeneration of sugarcane *in vitro* (Sani *et al.*, 2010; Kabir *et al.*, 2024). However, there are few reports on regenerating sugarcane through indirect organogenesis. This study was conducted to develop a reproducible protocol for sugarcane regeneration via indirect organogenesis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Explant Sterilization

Actively growing, healthy sugarcane tips of four varieties (BD98001, B1245, B3, M21-1988) were

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taken from a sugarcane plantation in the research farm at Centre of Dryland Agriculture (CDA), Bayero University Kano, Nigeria (11°58'50"N 8°28'46"E). The selected explants were thoroughly washed three times under tap water using liquid detergent and soaked in a 10% antifungal solution for 30 minutes. The explants were transferred to a laminar flow hood and surface sterilized by immersion in 70% ethanol for one minute, followed by treatment with 2% sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl₂) containing a drop of Tween 20 for 15 minutes. Explants were subsequently rinsed three times with sterile distilled water.

Callus Initiation

Explants were trimmed to four leaves thick and cut into 1.5 cm pieces and placed inside bottles (3 - 4 per bottle) containing callus induction media. The callus initiation media consisted of Murashige and Skoog basal medium (Murashige and Skoog, 1964) supplemented with 30% and fortified with 2.5 mg/L 2, 4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D). The media was solidified with 2 mg/L phytigel before autoclaving for 15 minutes at 121°C and 15 psi. After inoculation, the culture bottles were properly capped, sealed, and incubated in the dark at 25±2°C for three weeks.

Plantlets Regeneration and Acclimatization

After three weeks of incubation in the dark, the resulting calluses were divided into pieces (1cm diameter) and transferred to sugarcane regeneration media consisting of MS basal medium fortified with

2.5 mg/L or 3.0 mg/L 6-Benzylaminopurine (BAP) with 0.5 mg/L Naphthaleneacetic acid. Cultures were kept under a 16-hour photoperiod at 25±2°C for four weeks. After four weeks of incubation under light, data on the number of shoots, shoot length, and number of leaves were recorded for each treatment. Plantlets up to 4 cm in length were rooted on MS medium supplemented with 1.0 mg/L NAA, and plantlets with well-developed roots were acclimatized in plastic cups containing sterilized soil covered with transparent polyethylene bags. After two weeks, the bags were punched to gradually reduce the humidity and were finally removed after another two weeks. The seedlings were transferred to the greenhouse for further evaluations.

Experimental Design and Statistical Analysis

A completely randomized design was adopted with three replications, while data obtained were subjected to Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) using SPSS statistical software (Version 23), and mean difference was compared using Fisher's Least Significant Difference (LSD) at a 5% probability level.

RESULTS

The result showed no significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) among the varieties in the number of leaves and shoot length (cm), except number of shoots Figure 1. It was also observed that a higher number of fully developed plantlets was produced by the M21-1988 variety with 16 well-developed explants per callus.

Figure 1: Effect of Varieties on *in vitro* shoot regeneration in sugarcane

The effect of exogenous hormone treatment on *in vitro* regeneration of sugarcane showed significant ($p \leq 0.05$) effects of the treatments on the number of shoots, number of leaves, and length of shoots among the treatments. The number of shoots was significantly

higher in media fortified with 3.0 mg/l BAP + 0.5 mg/l NAA, which produced 20 plantlets per callus and the number of plantlets were significantly higher when compared with media fortified with 2.5mg/l BAP + 0.5mg/l NAA and the control which produced 11 and

9 plantlets, respectively (Figure 2). The number of leaves was significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) higher in media supplemented with 2.5 mg/l BAP + 0.5 mg/l NAA, having 7 leaves per plantlet, while 3.0 mg/l BAP + 0.5 mg/l and the control each recorded 5 leaves per

plantlet. Shoot length was higher in media supplemented with 2.5 mg/l BAP, 0.5 mg/l NAA, and then the control, which recorded 6.00 cm and 6.33 cm, and was significantly higher than media fortified with 3.0 mg/l BAP + 0.5 mg/l NAA.

Figure 2: Effect of exogenous hormones on *in vitro* shoot regeneration in sugarcane

There is a significant interaction ($p \leq 0.05$) between treatment and variety on the number of plantlets via indirect organogenesis in sugarcane (Table 1). The variety M21-1988 produces a significantly higher number of plantlets per callus when cultured on media fortified with 3.0 mg/l BAP + 0.5 mg/l NAA. This was

followed by an interaction between the variety BD98001 and 3.0 mg/l BAP + 0.5 mg/l NAA. These results were significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) higher than the number of shoots produced when the varieties were cultured on media fortified with 2.5 mg/l BAP + 0.5 mg/l NAA and the hormone interaction

Table 1: Variety \times Treatment interaction on shoot regeneration via indirect organogenesis in callus culture of sugarcane.

Varieties	Treatment		
	2.5mg/l BAP+ 0.5mg/l NAA	3.0mg/l BAP, 0.5mg/l NAA	Control
BD98001	13.00 \pm 1.41 ^c	22.00 \pm 3.49 ^b	8.00 \pm 1.41 ^d
B1245	12.00 \pm 4.95 ^c	14.00 \pm 3.54 ^c	7.00 \pm 0.71 ^d
B3	14.00 \pm 1.41 ^c	15.00 \pm 2.83 ^c	7.00 \pm 1.41 ^d
M21-1988	13.00 \pm 3.66 ^c	28.00 \pm 1.41 ^a	8.00 \pm 0.71 ^d

Values with the same alphabet within the column are not significantly different at $p < 0.05$

The B1245 variety cultured on media fortified with 3.0mg/l BAP + 0.5mg/l NAA showed a significant ($p < 0.05$) number of leaves. This was followed by interaction between M21-1988 and BD98001 with 2.5mg/l BAP + 0.5mg/l NAA, and B1245, BD98001, B3, and M21-1988 with 3.0mg/l BAP + 0.5mg/l NAA

(Table 2). Interaction was not significant for B3 and B1245 with 2.5mg/l BAP + 0.5mg/l NAA and the control. Similarly, there was no significant interaction recorded in this study between variety and treatment in plantlet length.

Table 2: Variety \times Treatment interaction on number of leaves in sugarcane plantlets

Variety	Treatment		
	2.5mg/l BAP, 0.5mg/l NAA	3.0mg/l BAP, 0.5mg/l NAA	Control
BD98001	5.00 \pm 1.41 ^{bc}	6.00 \pm 1.41 ^b	1.00 \pm 0.00 ^f
B1245	3.50 \pm 0.71 ^{cd}	8.50 \pm 0.71 ^a	1.50 \pm 0.71 ^{ef}
B3	4.00 \pm 1.41 ^c	5.00 \pm 0.00 ^{bc}	1.50 \pm 0.71 ^{ef}
M21-1988	6.50 \pm 2.12 ^b	5.00 \pm 1.41 ^{bc}	2.00 \pm 1.41 ^e

Values with the same alphabet within the column are not significantly different at $p < 0.05$

DISCUSSION

Callus formation began in most of the explants after seven days of culture in the dark and rapidly grew to cover the entire explant after four weeks of culture. Callus growth was rapid in the first two weeks of subculture on induction media, but the growth rate declined in the third and fourth weeks of subculture. The presence of 2, 4-D was critical for callus formation in the explant, as explants cultured on 2, 4-D-free media failed to form callus and degenerated after eight weeks of culture. 2, 4-D triggers the cellular transition processes from the differentiated cell to the embryogenic cell. This process is complex and includes dedifferentiation and cell division, which are modulated to metabolic and developmental reprogramming, conferring competence to the cells of the explants (de Morais Oliveira *et al.*, 2023). Two distinct callus types were observed in all the sugarcane varieties cultured: Compact nodular embryogenic callus, which was off-white and capable of proliferating globular structures, which subsequently developed into shoots. The second type of callus was a brownish watery non-embryogenic callus, which was loose in texture, and this callus was not capable of developing shoots. A similar observation was also reported in *Vanda spp.* by Budisantoso *et al.* (2017).

Regeneration of shoots was achieved in the embryogenic callus in all the sugarcane varieties evaluated in this study. Hence, 2.5mg/L 2, 4-D was found to be optimum for generating callus that will subsequently give rise to shoots via indirect organogenesis. Differences were, however, observed in the regeneration capacity of the sugarcane varieties, indicating that the varieties expressed differential responses in embryogenic callus induction in the presence of 2, 4-D. Previous reports indicated that different genotypes respond differently to varying 2, 4-D levels (Arzani & Mirodjagh, 1999; Zheng & Konzak, 1999). Organogenesis in callus culture starts with the development of a group of meristematic cells that respond to the factors within the system to initiate a primordium, which induces either a shoot or a root. The presence of exogenous cytokinin (BAP) and auxin (NAA) significantly increases the number of shoots regenerated when compared with the callus culture on hormone-free (control) media. Previous reports suggested that exogenous hormones determine the developmental fate of callus cells by regulating biosynthesis and distribution of endogenous hormones, triggering the specialized hormonal signalling required for cell differentiation (Su and Zhang, 2014). The Exogenous BAP and NAA used in this study

might control morphogenesis in the callus culture of sugarcane by controlling the levels and interaction between the endogenous hormones in callus cells. Cytokinins regulate cell proliferation, and auxins are involved in both cell proliferation and cell elongation processes. Generally, it is now established that hormonal interactions and their regulatory networks control the development of root and shoot meristems in callus culture. In this study, Plant generation has been achieved from sugarcane callus through indirect organogenesis. Although propagation in sugarcane could be achieved either by direct or indirect organogenesis, indirect organogenesis has by far more potential for mass clonal propagation of sugarcane. The protocol could be adapted for large-scale production of planting materials and future studies on *in vitro* mutagenesis and genetic transformation of sugarcane with genes of interest.

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